

Supplementary table 3 Baseline characteristics in anti-CCP2-positive and -negative RA

Characteristics	CCP2+	CCP2-	P-value
Age, median years (range) (N: 1,766 CCP2+ / 989 CCP2-)	54 (18-70)	57 (18-70)	<0.0001
Female, n (%) (N: 1,762 CCP2+ / 984 CCP2-)	1,261 (72)	701 (71)	0.9
Ever Smoker^a, n (%) (N: 1,385 CCP2+ / 813 CCP2-)	1007 (72.7)	508 (62.5)	<0.0001
HLA-DRB1 SE, n (%) (N: 1,385 CCP2+ / 813 CCP2-)	1,180 (85.2)	441 (54.2)	<0.0001
PTPN22, n (%) (N: 1,385 CCP2+ / 813 CCP2-)	427 (30.8)	222 (27.3)	0.02
DAS28, median (range) (N: 1,282 CCP2+ / 704 CCP2-)	5.11 (0.03-8.89)	5.21 (0.03-8.37)	0.053
CRP, median mg/L (range) (N: 1,357 CCP2+ / 739 CCP2-)	12 (0-332)	11 (0-221)	0.208

^a Ever smoker includes current and former smokers. Significant P-values are shown in bold.

CCP = cyclic citrullinated peptide; CRP = C-reactive protein; DAS28 = disease activity score using 28 joint counts; HLA = human leukocyte antigen; PTPN22 = protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22; SE = shared epitope.